

Chemical Speciation and Coordination Chemistry in Environmental Research

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Coordination chemistry plays an important role in fundamental life processes. In living systems metals are strongly bound at the active sites by metallo-enzymes. It is well-known that biochemistry is the coordination chemistry of living systems.

The metal ions occurring in fresh waters and polluted waters are tied up as complexes by the naturally occurring ligands and chelating agents such as humic substances. In fresh water copper(II) is fixed as copper(II)-humic acid complex and thereby rendered non-toxic to the biota. In marine organisms, such as crab, arsenic(III) exists as the non-toxic complex, arsenobetaine and safe for human consumption. On the other hand, the inorganic forms of arsenic(III) are toxic. Elemental mercury is not very toxic but the methyl derivatives are highly toxic and responsible for all fatal cases of mercury poisoning. It is thus important to have an understanding of the chemical species of an element in the environment. This leads us to chemical speciation which is an important aspect of environmental analysis and research. The state of art of speciation of some important elements - copper, lead, arsenic and mercury - is critically examined.

COORDINATION chemistry in biological environment :

Coordination chemistry plays an important role in Environmental Chemistry. It is well-known that complex compounds of magnesium (in chlorophyll) and iron (in hemoglobin) are vital to life processes.

Iron : Iron is ubiquitous in living systems. It is at the active centre of molecules responsible for oxygen and electron transport. It occurs in or is associated with several metalloenzymes such as nitrogenase, oxidases, reductases etc. Its mechanism in all these systems is not yet clearly understood. Only in cases of hemoglobin, ferredoxins and cytochromes the molecular structures and electronic properties of the active sites are known.

Iron is also found in the whole ranges of life forms from bacteria to man. It is abundant in the earth's crust and it has two readily interconvertible oxidation states. These are responsible for its participation in the early stages of evolution in many life processes.

Iron bacteria are interesting in the sense that they are not dependent on organic matter for growth. They thrive in a completely inorganic medium using CO₂ or other carbonate species as a carbon source. *Gallionella* grow in medium consisting of NH₄Cl, phosphates, mineral salts, CO₂ and solid FeS (energy source). The energy-yielding reaction is

Such types of bacteria (autotrophic) are involved in many geochemical processes because of their consumption and production of a wide range of minerals.

Gallionella secrete large quantities of Fe₂O₃ in the form of intricate branched structures. The bacterial cell grows at the end of a twisted stalk of Fe₂O₃. Electron microscope pictures reveal that the stalks consist of a number of strands of Fe₂O₃ secreted from one side of the cell. It is believed that special chelating agents called siderophores

($\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \quad \text{O}^- \\ || \quad | \\ \text{---C---N---} \end{array}$ hydroxamate moieties) are produced by bacteria and ejected into their environment to collect iron and transfer it through the cell wall into the cell.

Metalloenzymes : One of the major roles of metals in living systems is in metalloenzymes. This term is applied to enzymes that not only involve metal ion at the active site but bind the metal ion or ions strongly. At present several hundred metalloenzymes are known. They belong to the group of metalloproteins i.e. proteins which incorporate one or more metal atoms as a normal part of their structures. These include not only enzymes but respiratory proteins such as hemoglobin and myoglobin, electron transport proteins and metal storage proteins. The order of abundance of metals in the biosphere is Fe, Zn, Mg, Ca, Cu and K.

Coordination chemistry in aquatic environments :

The ligands occurring in natural and waste waters contain a variety of organic groups,

Carboxylate Aliphatic and aromatic amino groups

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These ligands complex most metal ions in unpolluted water and biological systems. They also bind to contaminant metal ions, e.g. Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Cd^{2+} . Complexation is likely to cause changes in oxidation state of the metal and may increase its solubility. The formation of insoluble complex compounds may remove metal ions from solution.

Naturally occurring chelating agents such as humic substances and amino acids are found in water and soil. The high concentration of chloride ion in sea water results in the formation of chloro-complexes of metal ions. Synthetic chelating agents such as sodium tripolyphosphates, sodium ethylenediaminetetraacetate (EDTA), sodium nitriloacetate (NTA) and sodium citrate are produced on a large scale in metal plating baths, industrial waste treatment, detergent formulation and food preparation. Small quantities of these compounds enter aquatic systems through water discharge.

Humic substances : These are the most important complexing agents occurring in nature. They are degradation-resistant materials formed during the decomposition of vegetation. They are high molecular weight polyelectrolytic macromolecules, the molecular weights ranging from a few hundred to tens of thousands. It is assumed that humic acid consists largely of condensation products of compounds such as catechol, syringaldehyde and 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid and the basic structure contains -O- and -N- linkages. The binding of metal ions by humic substances is one of their important environmental qualities. The binding can occur as chelation between COOH, phenolic OH or between two COOH groups or as complexation with a COOH group. Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} are strongly bound while Mg^{2+} is rather weakly bound. Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and Zn^{2+} are intermediate in their binding to humic substances.

Chemical speciation in environmental research :

The term chemical speciation actually means identification of inorganic, organometallic and organic species of an element/chemical in the environment. The chemical speciation is an important aspect of environmental analysis and research.

The biological activity or toxicity of an element depends on its species. In fresh water copper(II) is tied up as strong copper(II) - humic acid complex and thereby rendered non-toxic to the biota. Arsenic(III) in arsenite(III) is toxic but it makes a delicious sea food in crab meat where it is rendered non-toxic in the form of arsenobetaine, $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{As}^+\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-$. Mercury metal is not very toxic but in aquatic

environment dimethyl mercury $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg}$ and monomethyl mercury CH_3Hg^+ are highly toxic. The physical properties and chemical behaviour differ among different species of an element. These affect the transport of the element concerned in the environment and its toxicity to man and other organisms.

In the following sections a critical account of the state of art of the speciation scheme in general and speciation of some typical elements, such as copper, lead, arsenic and mercury using sophisticated instrumental techniques¹⁻⁴, is presented.

Speciation scheme : There are three routes for chemical speciation in water : (i) laboratory experiments using simplified systems, (ii) mathematical models employing experimental stability constants and (iii) analyses of actual water samples. These have been applied to Cu and Pb, the two relatively abundant metals in nature.

The determination of actual metal species in a water body is the most practical approach⁵. The first step in the speciation scheme is the separation of filterable and non-filterable forms, followed by further discrimination of the metal forms within each fraction. The particulate metal (non-filterable fraction) can be further discriminated using sequential extraction procedures by a series of extractants : MgCl_2 , NaOAc , NH_4OH , Cl^- - HOAc , H_2O_2 - NH_4OAc and HF - HClO_4 (Table 1)⁶.

A comprehensive speciation scheme is outlined⁶ for heavy metals in natural water (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

In relatively unpolluted water more of the non-filterable metals are transported within the crystalline solid phase. Thus they are not biologically available as are the metals in more polluted water which tend to be associated with organic matter and hydrous oxides of Fe and Mn. It is

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION PROCEDURE FOR SPECIATION OF PARTICULATE METALS

Extractant	Metal species
1 M MgCl ₂ (pH 7)	Exchangeable
1 M NaOAc (pH 5)	Bound to carbonates
0.04 M NH ₄ OH.HCl in 25% CH ₃ COOH at 96°	Bound to Fe—Mn—hydrous oxides
H ₂ O ₂ (pH 2, taken up in NH ₄ OAc in 20% HNO ₃)	Bound to organic matter
HF—HClO ₄	Residual

hard to distinguish between labile and non-labile metal in the filterable fractions. It depends on the electrochemical state of the metal and its tendency to deposit on a cathode — it is subsequently determined by Anodic Stripping Voltammetry (ASV) or taken up by an ion-exchange resin such as Chelex 100. Thus one is able to determine free metal ions and positively charged ion pairs as well as complexed metals which have fast dissociation kinetics.

The determination of total element in a sample for which reasonably good analytical methods are available can be time-consuming and expensive. The idea of analysing for every determinable form of every element is also not feasible. The best compromise is to conduct studies on a case-by-case basis and monitor by using the easier total element analyses, where available. For example, in a lake polluted by arsenic—source, it is sufficient to analyse once for several forms of As in water, in air above the lake and in the adjacent area, sediments, soil, plants and other biota. After this, total element analysis of lake water and ambient air serve the purpose of complete monitoring.

Speciation in air analysis¹ : The analysis step is preceded by preconcentration by cryogenic and cold trapping or reversible chemisorption or chemical reaction. Cryogenic trapping has often been used to concentrate small sample volumes (50–500 ml). An alternative is physical adsorption onto solid sorbents of various types. This is not suitable for large volume preconcentration of the more volatile trace compounds. In many speciation studies, the components sought are volatile at ambient temperatures. Thus (CH₃)₃As (b.p. 70°), (CH₃)₄Pb (b.p. 110°) and (CH₃)₂Hg (b.p. 96°) are present at very low level in the environment (below 10 mg m⁻³). For these species preconcentration of 100–1000 l or more is necessary and it can be achieved by chemical reaction or by reversible chemisorption. Chemical reaction approaches are the oldest involving simultaneous preconcentration and analysis for trace compounds in air. Ozone is detected by noting the chemiluminescence on a silica gel surface treated with Rhodamine-B. Pb-, Ag- and Hg-treated filters have been used to detect low concentrations of H₂S in air. Metal surfaces with specific activity for chemisorption of volatile compounds are known. AsH₃ and its methyl derivatives are adsorbed on clean Ag-

coated glassbeads from which the vapours are desorbed by warm dilute NaOH solution.

Speciation in water analysis¹ : Solvent extraction methods are extensively used for the preconcentration of water samples prior to analysis by atomic absorption spectrometry. Extraction has to be followed by separation before analysis for speciation purposes. Arsenic(III) and organoarsenic compounds are converted under optimum conditions to the diethyldithiocarbamate derivatives, extracted into organic solvent and analysed by gas chromatography.

Speciation of selected elements :

Copper : Laboratory studies on copper are easy to perform. They are based on the isolation of one or two parameters and study the effect of these on chemistry of the metal. Thus humic acids complex Cu²⁺ considerably. These complexed species can be discriminated by ultrafiltration which will retain the high molecular weight complexes on the filter and pass the uncomplexed metal. At pH 6–8 considerable complexation of Cu occurs in natural water whereby the toxicity of Cu to aquatic life is reduced. Mathematical modelling provides interesting studies, though these deviate markedly from real situations. As one proceeds from fresh water to sea water along a model estuary, it is observed that in fresh water Cu—humic acid complex dominates while in sea water the dominating species are Cu(OH)₂ and CuCO₃ and the minor species are CuOH⁺, Cu²⁺ and CuHCO₃⁺. Such models are however open to question; the conditional stability constants of all the complex species are not accurately known and all significant interactions are not taken into account.

Lead : In sea water Pb is mainly associated with colloidal inorganic particles; Pb, adsorbed on colloidal Fe(OH)₃ and MnO₂. Pb is also incorporated with organic particles and remains of living organisms. In fresh water at pH 6, Pb is mainly in the form of an inorganic, non-colloidal, non-labile species, probably Pb₂(OH)₂CO₃. At higher pH values of most surface water, Pb is more likely to be associated with colloidal matter.

Air-borne Pb compounds are found in both gaseous and particulate matter. X-Ray powder diffraction studies confirm the presence of PbSO₄, (NH₄)₂SO₄, Pb₃O₄, PbO, PbSO₄ etc. in street dust and PbSO₄, PbO and PbS in roadside soil. Automotive Pb compounds in roadside air are reported to consist of PbSO₄, (NH₄)₂SO₄, PbBrCl. 2NH₄Cl, PbBrCl.(NH₄)₂BrCl etc.

Alkyl lead compounds in the environment due to automotive emissions have been separated and characterised⁷. Tetraalkyl lead compounds in the environment undergo decomposition to form highly water-soluble ionic alkyl lead, PbR₄ → PbR₃⁺ → PbR₂²⁺ → PbR³⁺ → Pb⁴⁺, where, R is methyl or ethyl. The stability sequence appears to be PbMe₄ > PbEt₄ > PbMe₃. The speciation of these

alkyl lead compounds has been accomplished by application of several sophisticated techniques, such as gas chromatography, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, gas chromatography-atomic absorption spectrometry etc.

Arsenic : As has drawn considerable attention in view of its toxicity. As analyses are generally carried out by the silver diethyldithiocarbamate spectrophotometric method. The methyl- and dimethyl-arsenic acid compounds are also reduced by the same method but they give different absorption curves. The method is convenient for speciation in the 10^{-6} g As or greater sample range and initially used for analysis of bovine urine for inorganic and methyl arsenic content.

Sodium borohydride reduction is widely used for total As content using atomic absorption spectrophotometry. It is also used for reduction of alkyl and aryl arsenic compounds. Arsenic speciation in air samples is carried out using a glass-wool filter to trap the particulates followed by silvered glass beads to trap volatile arsines. The arsines are removed by dilute NaOH wash and analysed as above after NaBH_4 reduction. Ambient air contains As mostly as the inorganic species, some $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{As}$ in the vapour form and some methyl arsenic compounds as particulates.

Human urine consists of As species (average values, Mg/l : As^{III} 1.9, As^{V} 3.9, $\text{CH}_3\text{As}(\text{OH})_2$ 1.8, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{AsO}(\text{OH})$ 1.50 and total As, 22.5 ± 8.5). Speciation of As in water, urine and biological samples has been conducted by I^- reduction instead of NaBH_4 . As^{V} compounds are converted to iodide in presence of I^- , which are allowed to react to diethylammonium diethyl dithiocarbamate to yield the As-complexes of diethyl dithiocarbamate : $\text{As}[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NCS}_2]_2$, $\text{CH}_3\text{-As}[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{N-CS}_2]$, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{-As}[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{N-CS}_2]$. These complexes are then separated by gas chromatography with electron capture detector. The detection limits are 73, 40 and 15 ng dm^{-3} for inorganic As, methyl arsenic and dimethyl arsenic compounds respectively.

High pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC) in conjunction with graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrophotometer (GF AAS) has been successfully employed to confirm the presence of arsenobetaine, $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{As}^+\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-$ in crab meat⁸. Similarly, HPLC in conjunction with IPC (inductively coupled plasma emission spectrometer) is used to confirm the presence of considerable amounts of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{AsOOH}$ and small amounts of arsenate in one herbicide⁹.

The environmental chemistry of As is summarised in Chart 1⁹.

Mercury : The history of chemical speciation actually dates back to the Minamata episode in 1953. Extensive research has been carried out since then on the aquatic chemistry of Hg, its biotransformation, toxicity to biota and monitoring and analytical techniques. It has been established that there is remarkable difference in toxicity between $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg}^+$, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg}$ and other species, viz. Hg^0 , Hg^{2+} etc. It is these methyl mercury compounds which are responsible for all the fatal incidents due to Hg poisoning. Hence it is of utmost importance to estimate the methyl mercury compounds in biological materials. The major approach in speciation is to distinguish between Hg^0 , Hg^{2+} , CH_3Hg^+ and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg}$.

The biomethylation of Hg is an important aspect of its environmental chemistry. A Co^{III} -containing vitamin B_{12} coenzyme is the essential co-factor for such reaction. A CH_3 group bonded to Co on the coenzyme is transferred enzymatically by methyl cobalamin to Hg^{2+} forming CH_3Hg^+ or $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg}$:

Chart 1. Environmental chemistry of As.

Chart 2. Environmental chemistry of Hg.

Acidic conditions favour $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{Hg}^+$ transformation. In neutral or alkaline water $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg}$ is formed. In a water body, methylcobalamin is produced by bacteria in the bottom mud from which the volatile $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg}$ escapes into water and partly into air. On the other hand, CH_3Hg^+ is soluble in water and concentrates in living organism, usually in the body lipids. The high levels of Hg in lake/river water and in fish tissues can thus be explained. Hg from its methyl compounds gets concentrated in fish tissue (lipid) and this biomagnification factor from water to fish may exceed 10^5 .

Speciation of Hg in air samples is based on specific absorption of Hg compounds. A stream of absorption tubes is used which after removal of particulate matter, separates HgCl_2 type compounds, CH_3HgCl -type compounds, Hg^0 and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg}$ from each other. Hg^0 is adsorbed on Ag-coated glassbeads and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Hg}$ on Au-coated glassbeads; HgCl_2 and CH_3HgCl are adsorbed on gas chromatographic solid supports treated with HCl and NaOH respectively. The detector used is a He-dc discharge emission (AES) type detector having detection limit about 0.01 ng Hg, with a preconcentration of 50–200 l of air. Less than 1 ng m^{-3} of Hg can be detected.

Water and biological samples are extracted by organic solvents to remove Hg compounds. The

organic extract is then subjected to gas chromatography using electron-capture detectors. Organomercurials can thus be separated, identified and estimated. Then the total Hg is estimated after oxidation of the sample using flameless atomic absorption spectrometry. Inorganic Hg is finally obtained from the difference between the two numbers.

The environmental chemistry of Hg is illustrated in Chart 2¹.

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